

**Studies in the Coagulation of Colloids from the Stand-
point of Smoluchowski's Theory. Part II.
Coagulation of Arsenious Sulphide Sol.**

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The coagulation of the arsenious sulphide sol during its transition from the *rapid* to the *slow* region has been examined employing the method used in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 11).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The same method of preparing the colloid was followed with the difference that the excess of hydrogen sulphide was removed by a current of hydrogen. A convenient amount of the sol (0.92 g. As_2S_3 per litre in all experiments), and of the coagulator solution were kept in a thermostat (15°); 10 c.c. from each of the solutions were introduced simultaneously at a known time in a reaction vessel kept in the thermostat. The coagulating sol was then filtered at different intervals. a , the initial colloid-content of the sol, $a-x$, that of the filtrate at a given time t , were estimated volumetrically by Kessler's method (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1863, 118, 17). Standard ferrous sulphate solution was used and the colloid-contents are expressed as g. of As_2S_3 per litre. The times taken for mixing the colloid and the coagulator solution, and for subsequent filtration were noted, and though small, are included in the time t . Curves A, B, C, D, E, in Fig. 1 show the progress of coagulation due to different electrolyte concentrations. β , the Smoluchowski's constant, cal-

culated from, $\beta = \frac{1}{t} \left[\sqrt{\frac{n_0}{n_t}} - 1 \right] \dots (1)$, and k , the bimolecular

constant were calculated as previously (Part I, *loc. cit.*) from values in Tables 1—5, which were obtained from the corresponding curves of Fig. 1. The calculation of results in Tables VI, VII is explained later.

FIG. 1.

A, 0.1370 N- H_2SO_4 in mixture.

B, 0.1265 N- " " "

C, 0.1174 N- " " "

D, 0.1028 N- " " "

E, 0.0912 N- " " "

TABLE I.

0.1370 N- H_2SO_4 . (Fig. 1. Curve A.)								
Time (min.) ...	1	2	4	6	8	10	14	16
$a-x$...	0.70	0.51	0.36	0.27	0.22	0.18	0.14	0.12
β ...	0.15	0.17	0.15	0.14	0.13	0.126	0.11	0.10
x ...	0.30	0.49	0.64	0.73	0.78	0.82	0.86	0.88
k ...	0.31	0.40	0.39	0.40	0.40	0.41	0.40	0.42

TABLE II.

0.1265 N- H_2SO_4 . (Fig. 1. Curve B.)								
Time (min.) ...	1	2	4	8	11	14	16	18
$a-x$...	0.75	0.68	0.61	0.54	0.50	0.45	0.43	0.41
β ...	0.11	0.082	0.056	0.038	0.032	0.030	0.029	0.029
x ...	0.25	0.32	0.39	0.46	0.50	0.55	0.57	0.59
k ...	0.23	0.18	0.13	0.088	0.076	0.075	0.071	0.069

TABLE III.

0.1174 N-H₂SO₄. (Fig. 1. Curve C.)

Time (min.) ...	1	2	4	6	10	12	14	16	18
$a-x$...	0.77	0.71	0.67	0.65	0.63	0.615	0.595	0.555	0.505
β ...	0.11	0.069	0.043	0.031	0.021	0.019	0.019	0.018	0.019
x ...	0.23	0.29	0.33	0.35	0.37	0.385	0.405	0.445	0.495
k ..	0.20	0.15	0.093	0.069	0.046	0.041	0.039	0.041	0.045

TABLE IV.

0.1028 N-H₂SO₄. (Fig. 1. Curve D.)

Time (min.) ...	1	2	5	10	15
$a-x$...	0.84	0.75	0.69	0.67	0.645
β ...	0.046	0.05	0.031	0.017	0.013
x ...	0.16	0.25	0.31	0.33	0.355
k ...	0.19	0.17	0.09	0.049	0.037

TABLE V.

0.0912 N-H₂SO₄. (Fig. 1. Curve E.)

Time (min.) ...	2	5	10	20
$a-x$...	0.80	0.74	0.71	0.67
β ...	0.036	0.023	0.014	0.0086
x ...	0.20	0.26	0.29	0.33
k ...	0.13	0.07	0.041	0.025

TABLE VI.

 T for $a-x=0.69$ Curve A, taken as unity.

Coagulator.	Time (min.).	$T_*/T.$	C/C_*	$P.$
A	1.15	1.0	—	—
B	1.7	1.48	1.082	5.0
C	2.75	2.39	1.167	5.6
D	5.0	4.35	1.332	5.1
E	15.0	13.1	1.502	6.3

TABLE VII.

 T for $a-x=0.67$, Curve B, taken as unity.

Coagulator.	Time (min.).	T_n/T .	C/C_n .	P.
A	1.2	0.52	0.924	8.2
B	2.3	1.0	1.0	—
C	4.0	1.74	1.08	7.4
D	9.3	4.04	1.23	6.7
E	20.0	8.7	1.39	6.6

Discussion.

From these results it is seen that for the maximum concentration of the electrolyte (Table I; Curve A, Fig. 1), β , the Smoluchowski's constant decreases on an average by about 7% during the first 8 minutes, in which about 74% of the sol is coagulated. This shows that the coagulation is very near the *rapid* region. Furthermore, the β —time curve in the above case (curve A, Fig. 2) lies apart from other curves corresponding to lower electrolyte concentrations (B—E, Fig. 2).

FIG. 2.

That this coagulation is almost *rapid* is also indicated by the tendency of k , the bimolecular constant to increase especially during the early stage (Table I; Curve A', Fig. 2), since the deduction from Smoluchowski's theory (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1917, 92, 129), *viz.*, that k should increase with time during both slow and rapid coagulations, holds in general only in the latter. The other series (Tables II—V) show a diminution of β with time, which is characteristic of slow coagulation. In these series, β decreases appreciably soon after the start of coagulation (Curves B—E, Fig. 2), which shows that the deviation from Smoluchowski's theory occurs mainly during the early stages. This is contrary to the observations of Mukherjee and Majumdar (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 785) on the slow coagulation of arsenious sulphide sol. Using the equation,

$$\Sigma n = n_0 / 1 + \beta t \quad \dots (2)$$

and assuming that Σn , the total number of particles is measured by the corresponding relative transparency, they found that the relative times (which are proportional to $1/\beta$) for a given value of Σn during different coagulations varied markedly after the initial stages of coagulation. Desai (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1928, 24, 191) has made similar observation in the slow coagulation of the tungstic acid sol, studied by a method similar to that employed by Mukherjee and Majumdar. Anderson's results on the slow coagulation of the gold sol, however, show just the opposite (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1924, 19, 623). He estimated the number of primaries at the time t by a colorimetric method due to Hatschek (*ibid.*), and calculated β from equation (2). It is seen from his results that the diminution of β resembles the present observations. It is suggested that this divergence of results regarding the variation of β during coagulation might in part be ascribed to the approximation involved in estimating Σn and n_t , which occur in equations (1) and (2) respectively. It may be pointed out that with the exception perhaps of the ultramicroscopic method, the continuous variability during coagulation, is practically the only criterion we have for adopting any given property as a measure of coagulation, especially in the case of polydisperse sols, (that is, in respect of Σn and n_t).

It is seen from the results in Tables I—V, that contrary to the requirements of Smoluchowski's theory, the bimolecular constant, k diminishes during coagulation. Similar results were obtained by

Anderson (*loc. cit.*) and by the authors in the slow coagulation of the antimony sulphide sol, using the present method of measuring coagulation (Part I, *loc. cit.*). On plotting k against coagulation time, regular curves were obtained, closely resembling the corresponding β —time curves in Fig. 2.

It is seen from Fig. 1 that the coagulation—time curves are not markedly *affine*, as would be the case if *slow* coagulation differed from *rapid*, only by a constant multiple of the velocity constant for the latter (Smoluchowski, *loc. cit.*). A number of workers (*cf.* Desai, *loc. cit.*) also Freundlich (*Colloid and Capillary Chemistry*, 1926, pp. 434-447) regard slow coagulation as essentially autocatalytic, and not amenable to a simple extension of Smoluchowski's equation deduced for rapid coagulation. The chief support for this view is derived from the fact that in a number of cases, (i) the coagulation—time curve has an **S**-shape, indicating acceleration of an initial slow change, and that, (ii) the following equation characteristic of an autocatalytic reaction holds:—

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_1 (1 - bx) (1 - x) \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where k_1 and b are constants; b is evaluable from the inflection on the x —time curve, and is practically independent of the coagulator concentration. k_1 corresponds to β . It will be seen from the results in Fig. 1 that the nature of the $(a-x)$ —time curves does not support (ii). k_1 in (i) was not constant in any of the series in Fig. 1, *e.g.* in the coagulation corresponding to the curve *C*, k_1 varied from 0.007 to 0.0058. In this connection it may be pointed out that Freundlich (*loc. cit.*), and Freundlich and Basu (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 115, 203) obtained evidence to show that in a number of coagulations, the observed autocatalysis was ascribable to secondary factors, such as part of the coagulum serving as coagulation nuclei, the removal of which by stirring eliminated the effect. Mukherjee and Majumdar (*loc. cit.*) found however without observing the special precautions as to stirring, etc., that a number of slow coagulations of colloidal arsenious sulphide sol did not show any sign of autocatalysis. It would appear, therefore, that whilst some changes might be subject to this effect, it can not be considered as a general characteristic of slow coagulation.

Such a characteristic is obtained in the very marked influence of the electrolyte concentration on the rate of slow coagulation. According to Paine (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1912, 16, 430), we have

$$\frac{T_n}{T} = \left(\frac{C}{C_n} \right)^P, \text{ or } P = \frac{\log T_n - \log T}{\log C - \log C_n} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

where T and T_n denote times for attaining the same stage of coagulation at electrolyte concentrations C and C_n respectively. The results of applying this equation to two series (curves A and B, Fig. 1) are given in Tables V and VI. It is seen that P varies from 5 to 8. The results of Paine (*loc. cit.*), Gann (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1916, 8, 63), Desai (*loc. cit.*), and of Hatschek (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 17, 499) show that the value of P depends upon the nature of the coagulating sol, and is approximately constant over a limited range of coagulator concentrations. We found that P varied considerably with the concentration of the coagulator taken as standard

(also, *cf.* Desai, *loc. cit.*). For instance with $\frac{a-x}{a} = .6$, and taking

the electrolyte concentration corresponding to curve C (Fig. 1) as standard, P was found to be as high as 16. It is to be anticipated therefore that the lower the coagulator concentration, C , the greater is the influence of a given increase in C , in increasing the rate of coagulation. This agrees with the change from almost nil coagulation to one of a low but finite rate, due to but a slight increase in the strength of the coagulator solution in the region of the so-called *threshold* concentration, which indicates a comparatively high value for P , and with the fact that in the *rapid* region, the rate of coagulation,

which is measured by $\frac{1}{T}$ in (4), is independent of C . It

follows therefore, that for large values of the last quantity P must tend to zero as a limit.

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